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PARAMETRIC OPTIMIZATION IN TURNING OPERATION OF A CNC LATHE MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

Turning is the process in which work piece is involves in machining operation, turn to getting desired shape at any dimension. As stainless steel is one of the most important and widely used materials in these days; so it is being chosen as the work piece material. The machining parameters are chosen to be cutting speed, feed and depth of cut. The main aim of the experiment is to minimize cutting forces (feed force, the thrust force and cutting force). The aim of the experiment is to minimize the forces, to reduce the chip thickness, to reduce the surface roughness and to reduce the tool wear & the main aim is to reduce operating cost. The experiment was carried out by a CNC lathe, and the forces were measured by a dynamometer. The mode of machining is dry machining. The System of all machine are FANUC but only a few machine are of SIMENS, analysis are used to obtain the optimum parameters for better machining. Minitab is statistical software which is used to do the analysis part.

Introduction

Now a day the main motive of the industries is to reduce cost and maximize their profit through improving their technology. In production engineering there is a lot of scope for improvement. A lot of efforts are being made to improve the productivity and machinability of the machines to satisfy the daily increasing needs. Sometime it happens that if we increase the surface finish or decrease the forces then the cost of machining increases in very large amount. So we have to optimize the things in such a way that it should

fulfill our both the needs i.e. the cost and quality of product should be optimized.

CURRENT RESEARCH:

A great deal of research has been conducted over the last 8 years in the Surface Machining group at the University of Waterloo in the area of complex sculptured surfaces. These surfaces, which are de need in detail later in this work, are essentially complicated and even artistic work pieces that have typically only been achievable through manual hand carving up until the last few years. In particular, research has been conducted in creating 3D sculptured surfaces using wood turning lathes as the machining centre. Many different lathe configurations and control strategies have been considered to best suit the machining of a sculptured surface. There also exists a large disconnect with most CNC systems between the development of a work piece model and creating the actual part. Quite often in industry, uniquely skilled workers are required to design the part models, create the necessary toolpaths and then program and run the machining system. These steps are often assisted with CAD/CAM packages, but still require a large amount of time and knowledge. A great deal of work has been done at the Surface Machining group to bridge this disconnect. Primarily, several software packages have been created for the direct conversion of a solid model into a toolpath that is usable by a machining centre. One goal of these works has been to make the machining process simpler and more intuitive; not just for industry, but also for the general consumer. The idea is to develop an affordable wood turning lathe that can create complex sculptured surfaces, with intuitive software that is run on a PC, from someone's home.

Recent Work

Having successfully proven the concept of machining complex sculptured surfaces on a CNC lathe, the research focus then shifted towards improving the quality and efficiency of the machining process. A new lathe structure was prototyped using an existing manual lathe design. Although larger and more expensive, the system was still significantly cheaper than a typical CNC lathe system. The intent was to create a system that could machine complex sculptured surfaces at speeds faster than those achieved with the previous lathe designs while also improving the surface quality of the part and keeping the cost of the system low. This type of system would be ideal for small businesses, which would benefit from a CNC machining system that used simplified control architecture. The main test pieces that were machined on this lathe were table legs. Table legs are one example of an item that is machined commercially on lathes. However, most table legs consist of axis-symmetric designs. Those that do not are typically hand carved. For this reason it was thought that machining table legs consisting of complex sculptured surface designs would be the perfect industrial application for demonstrating the abilities of the unique 3-axis CNC lathe. Below in figure 1.1 are a few illustrations of the wide variety of table legs that were machined with this CNC lathe system.

Figure 1.1: Example Table Leg Designs

LITERATURE REVIEW:

An effective methodology is needed to obtain the normalized minimum chip thickness. Liu et al. [1] has achieved this by making use of the thermo-mechanical properties of basic molecular mechanics and the theory of friction. The primary objective is to extend the knowledge of the minimum chip thickness values for other materials when they are subjected to different cutting conditions. Shear strain and strain rate with cutting temperature are important properties which were evaluated using these techniques. The cutting temperatures at both job-chip interface and tool-chip interface were considered. To facilitate the formulations, was used a model of slip-line field. This model represents the finished edge tool radius. To determine the conditions for the transition from plowing to Microcutting, the equation is used Kragelskii-Drujanov. To evaluate the effective flow stress at high strain rate, high temperature and high voltage, the model of

Johnson-Cook (aluminum alloy) and the model Oxley (for carbon steel) were combined. For the experimental design, the materials used are steel 1040 and Al 6082-T6. There are two contrasting ways in which has increased the cutting speed affects minimum chip thickness. In the first place, the cutting temperature increases with increased cutting speed leading to an increase of the effect thermal softening and consequent increase in the ductility. Thus, the minimum chip thickness increases too. Secondly, with increase of speed of cutting, deformation and effectively increase the speed of deformation which increases the effect of work hardening. Therefore, the minimum chip thickness and ductility decrease. It is seen that for the machining of carbon steels, chip of minimum thickness increases with the speed of the edge of the cutting tool and increases distance. Again, the higher the carbon content of the steels, the higher the minimum chip thickness. While the processing of aluminum, it is seen that the values of minimum thickness of chips remains constant over a wide range of cutting speeds and radio edge of the tool. Thus, for the machining of carbon steels, high-speed are not used while for the aluminum alloys of machining, high speeds are used for a higher productivity.

Analysis using Taguchi Method : TABLE NO-1

Cutting speed	feed	depth of cut	F _x	F _y	F _z	SR	TOOL WEAR	CHIP THICKNESS	SNRA1	STDE1	MEAN1
38.48	0.04	0.2	9	4	4	3.6	0.071	0.08	-14.0128	3.1823	4.1342
38.48	0.06	0.3	6	1	4	0.8	0.137	0.11	-10.3067	2.508	2.3874
38.48	0.08	0.4	6	4	6	2.5	0.057	0.14	-12.7533	2.519	3.7114
65.97	0.04	0.3	6	1	4	0.44	0.113	0.808	-10.2699	2.5745	2.3106
65.97	0.06	0.4	81	88	45	3.2	0.143	0.1	-35.1429	41.511	43.4686
65.97	0.08	0.2	4	6	6	2.6	0.078	0.11	-12.7768	2.4996	3.7356
112.31	0.04	0.4	6	1	6	0.8	0.094	0.08	-11.682	2.9597	2.7788
112.31	0.06	0.2	12	4	4	1.2	0.11	0.11	-15.5011	4.6537	4.262

Different curves has been plotted

Normalized value

TABLE NO-2

NORMALISED VALUE TABLE									
RUN NO.	Cutting speed	feed	depth of cut	Fx	Fy	Fz	SR	TOOL WEAR	CHIP THICKNESS
1	38.48	0.04	0.2	0.935	0.966	0.953	0	0.837	1
2	38.48	0.06	0.3	0.974	1	0.953	0.886	0.67	0.959
3	38.48	0.08	0.4	0.974	0.966	0.907	0.348	1	0.918
4	65.97	0.04	0.3	0.974	1	0.953	1	0.349	0
5	65.97	0.06	0.4	0	0	0	0.127	0	0.973
6	65.97	0.08	0.2	1	0.943	0.907	0.316	0.756	0.959
7	112.31	0.04	0.4	0.974	1	0.907	0.886	0.57	1
8	112.31	0.06	0.2	0.896	0.966	0.953	0.759	0.384	0.959
9	112.31	0.08	0.3	0.675	0.874	0.721	0.696	0.36	0.931

Deviation value=1-normalised value

TABLE NO-3

DEVIATION TABLE

Fx	Fy	Fz	SR	TOOL WEAR	CHIP THICKNESS
0.065	0.034	0.047	1	0.163	0
0.026	0	0.047	0.114	0.33	0.041
0.026	0.034	0.093	0.652	0	0.082
0.026	0	0.047	0	0.651	1
1	1	1	0.873	1	0.027
0	0.057	0.093	0.684	0.244	0.041
0.026	0	0.093	0.114	0.43	0
0.104	0.034	0.047	0.241	0.616	0.041
0.325	0.126	0.279	0.304	0.64	0.069

TABLE NO-4

Table for grey relational coefficient:

GRAY RELATIONAL CO-EFFICIENT					
Fx	Fy	Fz	SR	TOOL WEAR	CHIP THICKNESS
0.885	0.9363	1.000	0.333	0.754147813	1
0.951	1	1.000	0.814	0.602409639	0.924
0.951	0.9363	0.922	0.434	1	0.859
0.951	1	1.000	1	0.434404865	0.333
0.333	0.3333	0.365	0.364	0.333333333	0.949
0.828	0.9363	1.000	0.675	0.448028674	0.924
0.606	0.7987	0.702	0.622	0.438596491	0.879

Test Cases

Test cases have been developed to demonstrate the capabilities of the 3-axis CNC lathe and to evaluate the effectiveness of the changes to the system that have been described in the previous sections. This chapter presents the two test cases in detail, along with simulated and experimental results for machining these pieces. Each test model has its dimensions designed to be within the constraints of a typical table leg. The cross-section must be less than or equal to an 80mm diameter circle and the length of the part should be no more than 813mm in length. The first case consists of three basic shapes which are used to evaluate the speed and accuracy of the CNC lathe. The geometry presented attempts to highlight the unique machining ability of the lathe, while also demonstrating the speed and accuracy capabilities of the system in comparison to the original lathe design, as described in section 1.4. The second model is a simpler piece when considering geometry detail, but is difficult to machine nonetheless. This piece is used to demonstrate the concept of the smoothing algorithm proposed in section 6.3. The design of the piece is simpler to fully observe and evaluate the effects of the algorithm.

Test Case - Speed Testing
Toolpath Feature Selection

The geometry of the three test pieces was selected to represent as many features from different table leg designs as possible. This was done to make the results from the machining experiments relevant for the intended physical application of the 3-axis CNC lathe. Although relevant for intended products, creating a standard test piece also establishes a basis for comparison. In the future, if a new tool path method is developed or a new model and controller are implemented, these test pieces can be used as a comparison tool. The geometry used in this model will remain representative of the common features found in table leg designs, allowing new methods to test how they handle the different geometric features. Future modifications to the lathe system can use the results and observations drawn from these experiments as a gauge for their success.

Essentially, the creation of a table leg design is limited only by the imagination of the designer. This implies that the number of possible features that could be on a table leg is limitless. Already, from an existing set of fifty table leg designs, there is a large variety of features. Some of these features include; helices, letters, custom patterns and complex images. All of these features can be either embossed or debossed. Figure 7.1 illustrates some examples of these features. The tool path features selected for the test case must capture elements from some, if not all, of the above mentioned features for the experimental results to be considered broad enough to apply to any table leg that could be machined.

Figure 7.1: Table Leg Feature Examples

Conclusions and Future Work

This work presented several modifications and additions to a 3-axis CNC lathe with the intent to improve the overall machining speed of the system. A servo motor replaced a stepper motor on the speed limiting axis of the system. The radial axis of the lathe was found to be the limiting axis of the system because the dynamic demands on the axis were much higher than those of any other. A 1st-order linear model was identified to describe the modified axis and adaptive sliding mode theory was implemented for control. In initial testing, the model appeared to describe the dynamics of the x-axis satisfactorily and the controller was able to provide accurate positioning. The new trajectory generator that was implemented was able to create a smooth trajectory for each axis of motion. By using a 5th-order polynomial to create a smooth feed profile with continuous jerk motion, each axis had continuous acceleration and velocity profiles as well. Smooth profiles allow a motor to more easily follow the desired commands.

From the discussions of the experimental test cases presented in Chapter 7, these modifications appear to be successful in improving the speed of the system. Three test pieces were machined, each representing a basic body shape that is used in table leg designs. These were circle, square and triangle cross-sections. The difficulty of machining these basic shapes was increased by adding letters to the surfaces. The letters were used to represent the many different types of features that can exist on a table leg surface. The results of these experiments showed a successful increase in the machining speed of the CNC lathe compared to that of the original CNC lathe that was used before this work began. Each test case showed improvements to the reported speed from the original CNC lathe. The circular profile reduced machining time by approximately 52:91%, the square profile by 55:94% and the triangular profile by 58:07%, when comparing speeds of the rotational c-axis in rpm's. These results successfully demonstrated that the modifications to the 3-axis CNC lathe were able to increase the overall machining speed of the system while maintaining its ability to accurately machine complex sculptured surfaces. The results will also be of use as a new base line for speed testing if further modifications are made to the lathe system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The following results concluded from this experiment such that our main objective to optimize the modeling of process parameters of TURNING in stainless steel material. Such as

1. Here the optimal conditions of three process parameters are of feed rate 0.06, of cutting speed 32.98, depth of cut 0.3.
2. From the graph of larger-the-best of S/N ratio the minimum value occurred at **1.09** for feed rate in 2nd level, cutting speed in 1ST level and doc in 2nd level.
3. From the graph of residual versus fitted value the points are not form any standard platform. Hence it shows no error.
4. From the normal probability plot of residuals 5 points are closely placed at the slop of standardized residual versus percent.
5. In the normal probability plot of the residuals for mean and S/N ratio, All the points lie close to the line, Hence the experiment is correct.
6. In the ANOVA table for means the P-value has maximum value i.e. 0.831 in doc parameter. Hence doc is more significant than other factors.
7. The histogram plot represents normally distributed graph. Hence our experimental analysis is correct.

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